

Water

Perspectives on Nonpoint Source Pollution

PERSPECTIVES ON NONPOINT SOURCE POLLUTION

Proceedings of a National Conference

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FOREWORD

A cursory scan of this book will tell the reader that this is no ordinary proceedings of a conference. Indeed, the papers published here reflect a conference that was neither ordinary nor routine. These papers are very dissimilar—in length, in format, in tone. But they are alike in one vital way: each represents a slightly different perspective on the problem of nonpoint source pollution of our Nation's water.

And that was the intent: to gather together all those organizations and individuals concerned with this problem and to draw from them the most practical ways to deal with it.

As Assistant Administrator for Water at the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, Jack Ravan conceived this conference as an integral part of the Agency's approach to nonpoint source pollution. The other three components are discussed in this volume: ASIWPCA's survey of the States (being completed this fall); the Federal Nonpoint Source Task Force (which concluded its initial policy and strategy development at the end of 1984); and the Chesapeake Bay study now underway by the National Association of Conservation Districts.

Ravan's instructions for this conference were fourfold: (1) focus on drawing information from everybody involved with the problem; (2) find out how people throughout the country, at the local level, perceive the nonpoint source problem and how they believe it should be handled; (3) make the information flow from the grass roots upward—the Federal role was to listen and learn and exchange information, not to dominate; and (4) make it practical.

The conference steering committee took this charge very seriously, designing a structure that stimulated this flow of information. The program committee fleshed it out, using both submitted and invited presentations.

The result was essentially a practical dialog. Of course, it cannot be fully covered in these presentations, but they will serve to remind participants of the equally valuable informal exchanges that took place during the week in Kansas City.

Four basic themes evolved as the conference developed.

Practical, affordable solutions not imposed by Federal authority but worked out at the local level was the message of the keynoter, Congressman Pat Roberts of Kansas' First District.

The knowledge exists, participants reiterated throughout the sessions. Putting it to work is the next step.

Nonpoint source pollution is best solved at the local level, concluded Robert I. Broadbent, Assistant Secretary for Water and Science at the Department of the Interior, as he moderated the closing plenary session. Broadbent's conclusion was drawn from two days of listening to sessions and to individuals—and is repeated throughout this volume. Discussions of new State programs in Missouri and Maryland reinforce this belief.

Cooperation is the key. Ravan sounded that note at the opening plenary—and it continued to be apparent throughout the conference. Nearly 40 organizations came together to cosponsor this conference—many others were represented among the attendees. In the real-life capitals of this country, these organizations often find themselves at odds; many had never talked over their mutual concerns.

This conference certainly began such a dialog. And, as a session chairman, Roger Bollinger, observed, there was evident a willingness to talk, a maturity “that may allow us to truly begin solving our water quality problems.”

If a mature optimism and diversity of perspective were its hallmarks, then this conference's true success can be measured only by how we move forward from here. We have the information—in this volume, from this conference—but the communication established must translate into working together to improve the quality of our Nation's waters.

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Urban Issues—Construction Nonpoint Source Pollution: David Moreau, North Carolina Water Research Center, Raleigh.

Rural Issues—Noncoal Mining and Abandoned Land Reclamation: Roger Bollinger, Tennessee Valley Authority, Chattanooga, Tenn.

Rural Issues—Impact on Small Communities: Beth Ytell, Great Lakes Rural Network, Fremont, Ohio.

Land Use Issues—Management and Assessment: Eben Chesebrough, Massachusetts Division of Water Pollution Control, Westboro, Mass.; Robert Kirschner, Northeastern Illinois Planning Commission, Chicago, Ill.

Agricultural Issues—Western Experience: Dennis Grams, Nebraska Environmental Control, Lincoln, Neb.

Urban Issues—Hydrologic Modification and Septic Tanks: James Ruane, Tennessee Valley Authority, Chattanooga, Tenn.

Rural Issues—Silvicultural Nonpoint Source Pollution: Fred Haeussler, President, Society of American Foresters, Union Camp Corp., Savannah, Ga.

Case Studies: Byron Lord, Federal Highway Administration, McLean, Va.

Making Point/Nonpoint Abatement Tradeoffs: Carl Myers, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, Washington, D.C.

Data Availability and Needs: Henry Peskin, Resources for the Future, Washington, D.C.; Michael Smolen, North Carolina State University, Raleigh, N.C.

Water Quality Criteria and Standards: Alan Klimek, North Carolina Water Resources Research Center, Raleigh; Ron Jarman, Oklahoma Water Resources Board, Oklahoma City.

Sources and Fates of Materials Influencing Water Quality in the Agricultural Midwest: G. Richard Marzolf, Kansas State University, Manhattan; John Howland, Missouri Department of Natural Resources, Jefferson City.

Cross Boundary Nonpoint Source Pollution—The Implications: Mohamed El-Ashry, World Resources Institute, Washington, D.C.

Closing Plenary: Nonpoint Source Pollution Programs—Where We're Going: Robert Broadbent, Assistant Secretary for Water and Science, Department of the Interior.

GROSS EROSION RATES, SEDIMENT YIELDS, AND NUTRIENT YIELDS FOR LAKE ERIE TRIBUTARIES: IMPLICATIONS FOR TARGETING

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ABSTRACT

Studies of agricultural nonpoint pollution in selected watersheds within the Lake Erie Basin have included estimates of gross erosion rates, as well as measurements of sediment, phosphorus and nitrogen yields. These studies indicate that under conventional management practices average gross erosion rates for watersheds are not reliable indicators of the export of either soluble or sediment associated pollutants. Average gross erosion rates are not even good indicators of sediment yields. Consequently, factors other than gross erosion need to be considered in watershed level targeting for agricultural pollution abatement programs.

INTRODUCTION

In the early 1970's, measurements of phosphorus transport during runoff events in the Sandusky River suggested that phosphorus loading to Lake Erie from agricultural sources was being underestimated (Baker and Kramer, 1973). Extension of event monitoring to the lake's other major tributaries confirmed that agricultural sources were indeed larger than previously estimated. (U.S. Army Corps Eng. 1975). Phosphorus modeling studies for the lake indicated that phosphorus reductions from nonpoint sources would be necessary to achieve desired water quality in the lake. Consequently, a major focus of the U.S. Army Corps' Lake Erie Wastewater Management Study was to evaluate options for reducing phosphorus loading from agricultural sources (U.S. Army Corps Eng. 1979).

Part of the evaluation established water quality monitoring stations for a number of smaller watersheds, so that the relationships between watershed characteristics (e.g. land use, soils, slopes, and gross erosion) and pollutant export could be incorporated into the management plans. This paper summarizes some of the relationships between watershed characteristics and pollutant yields we have observed during these studies. In a companion paper in this volume, we have described some of the characteristics of sediment, nutrient, and pesticide transport in area streams and rivers (Baker et al. 1985). Our sampling methods and analytical procedures are summarized in that paper.

WATER QUALITY PROBLEMS ASSOCIATED WITH RURAL NONPOINT SOURCES IN THE LAKE ERIE BASIN

Phosphorus Loading to Lake Erie

Table 1 shows an estimate of the sources and amounts of total phosphorus and bioavailable phosphorus loading to

Lake Erie. This estimate draws upon several sources of information. The rural nonpoint phosphorus loads represent an average load for the 1970-80 period (Yaksich, 1983; Yaksich et al. 1985). The urban nonpoint load is based on the Lake Erie study (U.S. Army Corps Eng. 1982).

Point source phosphorus loading to the lake has been greatly reduced by phosphorus removal programs at municipal sewage treatment plants. The point source loads shown on Table 1 represent 1982 loading data. Since by 1982 most municipal dischargers were meeting the phosphorus removal requirements, little further reduction in municipal phosphorus loading can be expected.

The data for atmospheric inputs and Lake Huron inputs, as well as the municipal and industrial point source inputs, are taken from International Joint Commission sources (1983a, b). Direct point sources empty into river mouth areas, bays, or the nearshore zone of the lake while indirect point sources empty into streams and rivers in tributary watersheds. The estimates of bioavailable phosphorus loading are based on direct measurements by our laboratory (Baker, 1983b) and other bioavailability studies summarized by Sonzogni et al. (1982).

Rural nonpoint sources account for 60 percent of the total phosphorus loading and 56 percent of the bioavailable phosphorus loading to the lake. Soluble phosphorus derived from rural sources is a significant part of the rural bioavailable load.

The phosphorus target load for Lake Erie is 11,000 metric tons per year (Int. Joint Comm. 1984). The estimated load of 13,996, based on long-term nonpoint loads and 1982 point source load, exceeds the target load by 3,000 metric tons. Programs to achieve the additional 3,000 metric ton per year reduction are focusing on nonpoint sources, since the most cost-effective portions of municipal phosphorus removal programs have already been implemented (U.S. Army Corps Eng. 1982).

Other Water Quality Problems

The stream monitoring programs have also measured sediments, nitrates, and pesticides. Suspended sediments in area streams and rivers result in the usual problems associated with erosion (Clark et al. 1985). In the Sandusky River, nitrate concentrations exceed drinking water standards about 16 percent of the time in May, June, and July (Baker, 1985). Rivers are frequently used as public water supplies in northwestern Ohio, and nitrates are not removed in treatment.

Several soluble herbicides are present in the rivers in May and June and pass directly through conventional water treatment plants (Baker, 1983a). Until specific maximum contaminant levels or health advisory levels are established by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency for

the currently used pesticides that frequently occur in drinking water, assessing the significance of these exposures will be difficult.

STUDY WATERSHEDS

From 3 to 10 years of chemical sampling have been completed for the 15 watersheds listed in Table 2. The table includes the U.S. Geological Survey stream gauge station number, the drainage area, the mean discharge and per-

iod of hydrological sampling, the period of chemical sampling, and the number of samples analyzed for sediments and nutrients. The average annual runoff ranged from 23.2 cm for the Raisin River to 39.8 cm for the Cuyahoga River. Watershed sizes range from 44 to 16,359 km².

The land use within each watershed is summarized in Table 3. Except for the Cuyahoga River basin, cropland dominates land use for all of the watersheds. The geographical data system used for developing land use statis-

Table 1.—Total and bioavailable phosphorus loads for Lake Erie, based on 1982 point source loads, long-term nonpoint source loads, and recent studies of bioavailable phosphorus loads.

		Total Phosphorus		Bioavailable Phosphorus			
		Load Metric Tons	Percent of Total	Fraction Bioavailable	Load Tons	Percent of Total	
I.	NONPOINT SOURCES						
	Rural ¹						
	Particulate	80%	6720	48.0	.30	2016	31.2
	Soluble	20%	1680	12.0	.95	1596	24.7
	Subtotal		8400	60.0	(.43)	3612	55.9
	Urban ¹		900	6.4	.43	387	6.0
	Atmospheric ²		660	4.7	.38	251	3.9
	Total Nonpoint Source		9960	71.1		4250	65.8
II.	POINT SOURCE						
	Municipal						
	Flows > 1 MGD						
	Direct ²		1388	9.9	.70	972	15.0
	Indirect ³		1061	7.6	.35	371	5.7
	Flows < 1 MGD						
	Direct		110	0.8	.70	77	1.2
	Indirect		330	2.4	.35	116	1.8
	Subtotal		2889	20.6		1536	23.7
	Industrial ²		67	0.5	.50	34	0.5
	Total Point Sources		2956	21.1		1570	
III.	LAKE HURON INPUT ²		1080	7.7	.60	648	10.0
IV.	TOTAL LOADS		13,996	100		6468	100

¹Yaksich, 1983.
²J.J.C. 1983a.
³J.J.C. 1983b.
⁴Sonzogni et al. 1982; Baker 1983b.

Table 2.—Watershed areas, mean annual discharges, period of chemical sampling, and number of samples analyzed for the Lake Erie tributary monitoring program.

Transport Stations	U.S. Geological survey station number	Drainage Area Km ²	Mean Annual Discharge			Chemical Sampling Period	Number of Samples Analyzed
			Years of Record	m ³ /s	cm		
Sandusky River Stations							
1. Fremont	04198000	3,240	57	27.75	27.0	1974–84	4590 ²
2. Mexico	04197000	2,005	55	16.62	26.2	1974–81	2178
3. Upper Sandusky	04196500	722	57	6.967	28.5	1974–81	2973
4. Bucyrus	04196000	230	40	2.461	33.8	1974–81	2998
Sandusky River Tributaries							
5. Wolf Creek, East	04192450	213	5	1.82	27.0	1976–81	2425
6. Wolf Creek, West	04197300	171.5	5	1.34	24.6	1976–81	2419
7. Honey Creek, Melmore	04197100	386	7	3.908	32.0	1976–84	4595 ²
8. Honey Creek, New Wash.	04197020	44.0	3.908	(0.445) ¹	(32.0) ¹	1979–81; 83–84	2271 ²
9. Tymochtee Creek	04196800	593	19	4.956	26.3	1974–81	2471
10. Broken Sword Cr.	04196200	217	5	2.45	35.5	1976–81	2512
Other Lake Erie Tributaries							
11. Maumee River	04193500	16,359	58	139.5	26.8	1975–80; 82–84	3154 ²
12. Raisin	04176500	2,699	43	19.85	23.2	1982–84	805 ²
13. Cuyahoga	04208000	1,831	52	23.14	39.8	1981–84	1380 ²
14. Portage	04195500	1,109	51	9.091	25.9	1974–78	1856
15. Huron	04199000	961	31	8.496	27.9	1974–79	2027

¹Extrapolated from Honey Creek at Melmore.
²Sampling continued on 1985 program.

tics for Lake Erie watersheds has been summarized by Adams et al. (1982).

WATERSHED POLLUTANT EXPORT

The flux-weighted mean concentrations of sediments and nutrients at each of the transport stations are summarized in Table 4. These represent the flux-weighted averages for the entire period of chemical sampling and for the number of samples indicated in Table 2. For all of the stations, sampling is conducted throughout the year and consequently the averages reflect the seasonal distribution of storms that occurred during the sampling period.

One method of estimating mean annual pollutant export is to multiply the flux-weighted pollutant concentrations by the mean annual discharge. This procedure will provide an accurate mean annual load estimate so long as: (1) the flux-weighted average concentration accurately reflects current watershed responses to current weather and rainfall regimes in the region; and (2) the mean annual discharge for the period of record reflects contemporary watershed responses to current weather and rainfall regimes. The latter condition does not appear to be met since the average discharges for the Maumee, Sandusky,

and Cuyahoga rivers during the 1973-83 period are higher than long-term average discharges (as of 1983), by 17 percent, 26 percent and 30 percent respectively. Rather than attempt to adjust each watershed to current "average" discharges, the discharge data in Table 2 have been adjusted to long-term stations (Baker, 1983c). Other methods of using these data to estimate mean annual pollutant loads have been discussed by Baker (1984).

In Table 5, the mean annual loads of sediments and nutrients are expressed on a unit area yield basis. For each watershed the mean annual load was divided by the total watershed area to determine unit area yields. The gross erosion rates, as calculated in the Lake Erie study (Logan et al. 1982), are also listed for each watershed. The unit area total phosphorus yield of 1.26 kg/ha/year for the Sandusky Basin calculated by this method is significantly lower than the 10-year average export of 1.55 kg/ha/year actually measured at the station (Baker et al. 1985).

The unit area yields shown in Table 5 reflect the inputs of both point and nonpoint sources. For the parameters shown in Table 5, point sources constitute significant inputs only for phosphorus and for certain watersheds. Table 6 illustrates the typical procedure of correcting for

Table 3.—Watershed land use for the Lake Erie tributary nutrient and sediment transport stations.

Transport Stations	Cropland %	Pasture %	Forest %	Water %	Other %
Sandusky River Stations					
1. Fremont	79.9	2.3	8.9	2.0	6.8
2. Mexico	80.3	2.3	8.7	2.1	6.6
3. Upper Sandusky	78.0	3.4	9.1	2.0	7.5
4. Bucyrus	73.3	4.9	9.4	2.1	10.2
Sandusky River Tributaries					
5. Wolf Creek, East	81.9	2.7	6.3	2.0	7.0
6. Wolf Creek, West	83.3	1.4	4.7	3.1	7.6
7. Honey Creek, Melmore	82.6	0.6	10.0	0.5	6.3
8. Honey Creek, New Wash.	89.1	—	7.5	—	3.4
9. Tymochtee Creek	84.0	1.2	7.6	2.3	4.8
10. Broken Sword Creek	84.7	1.4	8.5	1.3	4.1
Other Lake Erie Tributaries					
11. Maumee River	75.6	3.2	8.4	3.5	9.4
12. Raisin	67.1	6.8	9.0	3.0	14.1
13. Cuyahoga	4.2	43.1	29.1	3.0	20.6
14. Portage	85.5	3.6	5.6	0.9	4.3
15. Huron	75.3	3.5	12.5	2.2	6.4

Table 4.—Flux weighted mean concentrations of sediments and nutrients at the transport stations for the period of chemical sampling.

Transport Stations	Suspended Solids mg/L	Total Phosphorus mg/L	Soluble Reactive Phosphorus mg/L	Nitrate + Nitrite-N mg/L	Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen mg/L
Sandusky River Stations					
1. Fremont	249	0.468	0.084	4.61	1.73
2. Mexico	230	0.409	0.061	4.32	—
3. Upper Sandusky	312	0.583	0.126	4.60	—
4. Bucyrus	273	0.633	0.199	3.71	—
Sandusky River Tributaries					
5. Wolf Creek, East	246	0.479	0.109	5.32	—
6. Wolf Creek, West	251	0.461	0.089	6.95	—
7. Honey Creek, Melmore	198	0.413	0.074	4.79	1.79
8. Honey Creek, New Wash.	254	0.458	0.088	5.05	1.81
9. Tymochtee Creek	231	0.424	0.065	5.60	—
10. Broken Sword Creek	312	0.479	0.064	5.08	—
Other Lake Erie Tributaries					
11. Maumee River	218	0.474	0.090	5.13	1.85
12. Raisin	81.1	0.238	0.046	3.51	1.23
13. Cuyahoga	188	0.428	0.105	1.82	1.36
14. Portage	164	0.402	0.119	5.89	—
15. Huron	220	0.362	0.104	3.61	—

point source inputs. Point source inputs, expressed on a unit area basis, are subtracted from the total unit area yield to determine a unit area nonpoint yield. This procedure assumes 100 percent delivery of point source phosphorus through the stream system.

The point source inputs for the Maumee River, Sandusky River-Fremont, Honey Creek-Melmore, and Sandusky River-Bucyrus reflect inputs from all municipal sewage treatment plants within the watershed. For the Raisin River and the Cuyahoga River, only sewage treatment plants with flows greater than 1 million gallons per day were included. Consequently, the nonpoint yields for the Raisin River and Cuyahoga River are probably being overestimated.

DISCUSSION

In general, the unit area yields of total phosphorus and total nitrogen (nitrate-N + total Kjeldahl nitrogen) in Lake Erie tributaries are much larger than the average values cited for agricultural lands. Based on a thorough review of the literature on loading studies, Rast and Lee (1983) recommended the use of 0.5 kg/ha/year and 5 kg/ha/year, respectively, for estimating total phosphorus and total nitrogen inputs into lakes from agricultural watersheds. The total phosphorus yields from the Maumee and Sandusky river basins are 2.5 times higher than these national averages. Total nitrogen yields in northwestern Ohio rivers are 3.5 times higher than the average values. These high rates of nutrient export occur even though the average gross erosion rates of 4.1 to 9.8 tons/ha/year (1.9 to 4.4 short tons/acre/year) for these watersheds are lower than the average for cropland in the United States.

Within the study watersheds, average gross erosion is not a consistent indicator of pollutant yields. In Table 7 the ratios of average gross erosion rates and yields of suspended sediments, nonpoint total phosphorus, soluble phosphorus, and nitrates are shown for three pairs of watersheds. The gross erosion rate is 2.2 times higher for the Broken Sword watershed than for the Wolf Creek West watershed, while the suspended solids and total phosphorus yields are 1.79 and 1.50 times higher, respectively. The gross erosion rate in the Honey Creek watershed is 1.6 times higher than Wolf Creek West, yet the suspended solids and nonpoint phosphorus yields are essentially the same.

The Raisin River watershed has the highest gross erosion rate—1.18 times higher than that of the Sandusky

Table 6.—Calculation of nonpoint phosphorus yields at representative transport stations.

Watershed	Total-P Export kg/ha/yr	Point		Percent Nonpoint
		Source-P Input kg/ha/yr	Non Pt. P-Export kg/ha/yr	
Maumee R.	1.27	0.20	1.07	84
Sandusky R., Fremont	1.26	0.14	1.14	89
Cuyahoga R.	1.71	1.11	0.60	35
Raisin R.	0.55	0.11	0.44	80
Honey Cr. Sandusky R., Bucyrus	1.32	0.09	1.23	93
	2.14	1.17	0.97	45

River watershed. The sediment and nonpoint total phosphorus yields for the Raisin are only 0.27 and 0.38 of those for the Sandusky. In part, the higher sediment and phosphorus deliveries from the Sandusky Basin result from finer textured soils.

Land use effects are evident in the data of Tables 5 and 6. The Cuyahoga Basin, which has a small percentage of cropland, has relatively low nitrate and nonpoint phosphorus yields. Stations impacted by large proportions of point source inputs (e.g. the Sandusky River Bucyrus station and the Cuyahoga stations) have high soluble reactive phosphorus yields.

Watershed size has little effect on suspended sediment and nutrient yields. The Maumee, Sandusky, and Honey Creek watersheds all have similar unit area exports. This suggests that instream delivery losses do not increase with watershed size for this region.

These studies do not support the use of the universal soil loss equation to select specific watersheds for targeted nonpoint phosphorus control programs. Instead, an areawide program to support best management practice (BMP) implementation on critical areas, regardless of sub-watershed boundaries, would likely result in the most cost efficient reductions in sediment and particulate phosphorus loads to Lake Erie.

The source areas for high nitrate concentrations in this region are the tile-drained fields. Fertilizer BMP's need to be implemented throughout this region. Since much of the soluble phosphorus export occurs in the winter season (Baker et al. 1985), the contributing areas are probably much larger than those for sediment and particulate phosphorus.

Table 5.—Gross erosion rates and unit area yields of sediments and nutrients at the transport stations.

Transport Stations	Gross Erosion Rate kg/ha/yr	Suspended Solids kg/ha/yr	Total Phosphorus kg/ha/yr	Soluble Reactive Phosphorus kg/ha/yr	Nitrate + Nitrate-N kg/ha/yr	Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen kg/ha/yr
Sandusky River Stations						
1. Fremont	8,250	673	1.26	0.22	12.5	4.68
2. Mexico	9,370	601	1.07	0.16	11.3	—
3. Upper Sandusky	9,350	950	1.78	0.38	14.0	—
4. Bucyrus	7,850	922	2.14	0.67	12.5	—
Sandusky River Tributaries						
5. Wolf Creek, East	5,110	663	1.29	0.29	14.3	—
6. Wolf Creek, West	4,190	619	1.14	0.22	17.1	—
7. Honey Creek, Melmore	6,860	633	1.32	0.24	15.3	5.72
8. Honey Creek, New Wash.	7,060	811	1.46	0.28	16.1	5.78
9. Tymochtee Creek	8,410	609	1.12	0.17	14.8	—
10. Broken Sword Creek	9,390	1,110	1.71	0.23	18.1	—
Other Lake Erie Tributaries						
11. Maumee River	6,840	585	1.27	0.24	13.8	4.97
12. Raisin	9,750	188	0.55	0.11	8.1	2.85
13. Cuyahoga	—	749	1.71	0.42	7.3	5.42
14. Portage	5,000	424	1.04	0.31	15.2	—
15. Huron	7,510	614	1.01	0.29	10.1	—

Table 7.—Comparison of erosion rate and nonpoint yields for representative watersheds.

Watershed	Gross Erosion kg/ha/yr	SS kg/ha/yr	Nonpoint TP kg/ha/yr	SRP kg/ha/yr	NO ₃ kg/ha/yr
Broken Sword	9,390	1,110	1.71	0.23	18.1
Wolf, East	4,190	619	1.14	0.22	17.1
Ratio—Broken Sword: Wolf East	2.24	1.79	1.50	1.04	1.06
Honey Creek	6,860	63	1.23	0.24	15.3
Wolf, East	4,190	619	1.14	0.22	17.1
Ratio—Honey: Wolf East	1.63	1.02	1.08	1.09	0.89
Raisin River	9,750	188	0.44	0.11	8.1
Sandusky River	8,250	673	1.14	0.22	12.5
Ratio—Raisin R: Sandusky R.	1.18	0.27	0.38	0.50	0.65

The timing of pesticide export during storm events suggests that the contributing areas are those from which surface runoff water reaches stream systems. This will vary considerably from year to year depending on rainfall amounts and intensities.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The nonpoint source nutrient exports from Lake Erie tributaries are very high relative to average agricultural export rates even though gross erosion rates in these watersheds are low.
2. Within this region, average gross erosion rates for watersheds are not reliable indicators of sediment and nutrient yields.
3. Contributing areas for nitrate and soluble phosphorus probably encompass a larger portion of the land surface than contributing areas for sediment and pesticides.

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